

NOTES

Polarographic Behaviour of Thorium (IV) in Methanol and Acetonitrile Media

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The polarographic behaviour of thorium has been studied in 50% methanol and acetonitrile at the dme. A single well defined irreversible diffusion controlled cathodic wave was observed, which shifted towards more positive potentials with increase in temperature in both solvents. The effects of various factors such as concentration of Th⁴⁺ ion, drop time and temperature on the wave characteristics have been investigated. The values of Kinetic parameters—the transfer coefficient α and formal rate constant $K_{f,h}^\circ$ have been calculated by Koutecky's method and are 0.24, 0.21 and 1.78×10^{-22} cm/sec., 1.41×10^{-20} cm/s in methanol and acetonitrile respectively.

A survey of literature reveals that several investigators studied the polarographic behaviour of thorium (IV) in different supporting electrolytes and solvents. Patterson and Banks¹ and Larger² reported a catalytic wave of thorium in KCl in presence of excess of nitrate. Cozzi³ observed that the behaviour of thorium at dme was similar to that of zirconium except that its $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ was not independent of temperature and concentration. Masek⁴ reported the polarography of thorium in water, water-ethanol solutions and observed that the depolarizing effect of Th(IV) ions was due to the reduction of H⁺ ions from the aquothorium complexes. Sacho *et al.*⁵ reported an irreversible diffusion controlled wave of Th(IV) in DMSO and water-ethanol media using LiCl as supporting electrolyte. Gritzner *et al.*⁶ have also studied the polarography of thorium in DMF and DMS. In view of conflicting reports of earlier workers, it was considered worthwhile to investigate the polarographic behaviour of thorium in methanol and acetonitrile media for which there is no indication in the literature.

EXPERIMENTAL

A.R. Quality chemicals were used and their solution prepared in doubly distilled air-free conductivity water. Freshly prepared solutions were always used to avoid the effects of ageing and air oxidation. Triton X-100 and NaClO₄ were used as maximum suppressor and supporting electrolyte respectively.

A Cambridge polarograph in conjunction with thermostated H-cell was used for recording C-V curves. The capillary had the following characteristics $m = 1.471$ mg/sec. and $t = 3.52$ sec/drop at -0.40 V vs. S.C.E.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The reduction of thorium in methanol and acetonitrile has been found to be irreversible since for any given polarogram the slope of the plot of $\log i/(i_a - i)$ vs. $E_{d.e.}$ equals 0.056 V and 0.066 V respectively.

Fig. 1 represents the current-voltage curves of 0.4 mM Th^{4+} , 0.5 M NaClO_4 0.002% Triton X-100 in 50% methanol and acetonitrile. The half-wave reduction potentials are -1.404 V and -1.440 V vs. S.C.E. in methanol and acetonitrile respectively. Due to an irreversible reduction of Th^{4+} , it was considered worthwhile to investigate the kinetics of the electrode reaction.

Fig. 1. Polarogram of 0.4 mM Th^{4+} , 0.5 M NaClO_4 + 0.002% Triton X-100 in 50% methanol (curve 1) and acetonitrile (curve 2)

From Koutecky's⁷ treatment of an irreversible wave as modified by Meites and Israel⁸ it follows that for a cathodic wave

$$E = E_{\frac{1}{2}}^0 - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n} \log \frac{i}{(i_a - i)} \quad \dots (1)$$

with

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}}^0 = -0.2412 + \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{1.349 K_{f,h}^0 t^{\frac{1}{2}}}{D_0^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad \dots (2)$$

(E and $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ are referred to S.C.E.).

The values of $K_{f,h}^0$ and α were calculated by applying equation (1) and (2). Since ' t ' does not vary appreciably over the range of potential covered by the rising part of the wave due to the reduction of Th^{4+} , it was not considered necessary to apply correction for i^0 . The values of transfer coefficient α and formal rate constant $K_{f,h}^0$ of the electrode process in methanol and acetonitrile are 0.24, 0.21 and 1.78×10^{-22} cm/s and 1.4×10^{-20} cm/s respectively.

Effect of Th^{4+} ion concentration : Polarograms of solutions containing different concentrations of thorium in presence of 0.5 M $NaClO_4$ and 0.002% Triton X-100 in 50% solvents were recorded. It is observed that upto 1.0 mM Th^{4+} , the limiting current is found to be proportional to Th^{4+} ion concentration in the case of acetonitrile but the same does not hold good in methanolic media (Table 1). The variation of $E_{1/2}$ with Th^{4+} concentration indicates the irreversible nature of the wave. The values of $i_{d/c}$ and diffusion current constants are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Effect of Th^{4+} ion concentration 0.5 M $NaClO_4$ +0.002% Triton X-100 in 50% non-aqueous media

Concentration of Th^{4+} (mM)	Methanol			Acetonitrile		
	i_d	i_d/C	$-E_{1/2}(V)$	i_d	i_d/C	$-E_{1/2}(V)$
0.15	1.00	6.60	1.440	1.25	8.33	1.540
0.25	1.90	7.60	1.510	—	—	—
0.30	—	—	—	2.50	8.83	1.560
0.40	2.70	6.75	1.404	3.35	8.37	1.440
0.50	3.80	7.40	1.500	4.35	8.60	1.570
1.00	7.50	7.50	1.495	8.35	8.35	1.530

Effect of Hg. pressure : A series of polarograms of 0.4 mM Th^{4+} were recorded at different heights of mercury column in both solvents. The linear plots of i_d vs. \sqrt{h} (Fig. 2) show the diffusion controlled nature of the wave.

Fig. 2. Plots of i_d vs. \sqrt{h} .

Effect of temperature : A solution of 0.4 mM Th^{4+} , was polarographed at various temperatures from 20°–45°. The limiting current is found to vary linearly with temperature upto 35° beyond which it increases markedly with temperature indicating kinetically

controlled nature of the wave at higher temperatures. The values of temperature coefficient of i_d for each temperature intervals calculated by Nejedly's method¹⁰ are shown in Table 2. That the half-wave potential shifted towards more positive potential with increase in temperature indicates the easier reduction of Th^{4+} at higher temperatures.

TABLE 2

Effect of temperature 0.4 mM Th⁴⁺ + 0.5 M NaClO₄ + 0.002% Triton X-100 in 50% non-aqueous media

Temperature °C	Methanol			Acetonitrile		
	i_d (μA)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	Temp. Coefficient	i_d (μA)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	Temp. Coefficient
20	2.70	1.403	—	3.35	1.440	—
30	3.50	1.345	2.96	3.65	1.398	0.89
35	3.90	1.335	2.96	3.75	1.390	0.72
40	4.35	1.315	3.42	4.20	1.355	1.26
45	5.15	1.295	3.63	4.50	1.335	1.37

Our results conclusively prove that the polarographic reduction of Th^{4+} in methanol and acetonitrile media is irreversible and diffusion controlled. These observations are in agreement with the findings of Sancho⁵, but do not support the views of Masek⁴.

REFERENCES

1. J. H. Patterson and C. V. Banks, *Analyt. Chem.*, 1948, **20**, 167.
2. A. Larger, *Ind. Engg. Chem. (Anal. Ed.)*, 1940, **12**, 511.
3. D. Cozzi, 'Proceedings of International Congress of pure and applied Chemistry', VII p. 57-68. (International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry, London), 1947.
4. Masek, *Chem. Listy*, 1958, **7**, 52.
5. J. Sancho, J. Almagro and A. Pujnte, *Anales Real Soc. Espan. Fis. Quim (Madrid)*, 1966, **62**, 1087; *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1968, **16**, 77.
6. G. Gritzner, V. Gitmann and M. Michlmayer, *Z. Anal. Chem.* 1967, **224**, 245.
7. J. Koustecky, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1953, **18**, 597.
8. L. Meites and Y. Israel, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4903.
9. L. Meites in 'Polarographic Techniques', 1966, p. 241, Interscience, New York.
10. V. Nejedly, *Coll. Trav. Chim. Tcheosl.*, 1929, **1**, 319.